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Probabilistic explorations of citation contexts: Citation roles and subject content of scientific references

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Abstract

In this preliminary study, we use natural language processing methods with an overarching goal to contribute toward a model that can link the *what* is cited in the text with the *how*. Using the context of cited references as *citances* derived from the Semantic Scholar Open Research Corpus, we investigate how the content of these citances can be enriched by semantically related words from an external vocabulary. Additionally, we explore what possible roles a reference may have in a scientific text, as indicated by verbal clues in the citances.

We show that semantically enriched subject descriptions seem to generate automatic content representations of references that contribute to a higher clustering effectiveness, while we find that determining which verb phrases that are indicative of citation roles and therefore can be expected to appear frequently in citation contexts, but infrequently elsewhere, it is possible to distinguish between disciplinary differences using the notion of integrative and dispersed citation practices.

Introduction

Since the late 1970s, researchers following the lead of, among others, Henry Small have published studies that focus on the (co-)citation context of cited documents (Small, 1979; Small, 1980; Small & Greenlee, 1980). Here, he delineated the “citation in context analysis”, wherein, for each document cited by several other documents, he identified the in-text passages in the citing documents that surrounded the cited document.

Hjørland (1992) states that the *subject* of a document can be understood as the epistemological potential of the document, i.e., the potential understanding and use of the document in different contexts. A *citance* is in this work regarded as a contiguous sequence of sentences in the context of a citation (cf. the definition provided by Nakov et al., 2004). As such, the citance is expected to be subject-wise related to the reference, so that the citance and the reference are conceptually overlapping. In other words, a portion of the words in the citance are expected to be *subject descriptors* of the reference.

One aim of this study is to use natural language processing methods to explore what possible roles a reference may have in a scientific text, as indicated by verbal clues in the citances.

Another aim is to investigate how the content of citances can be enriched by semantically related words from an external vocabulary to generate automatic content representations of references that contribute to a higher retrieval and classification effectiveness. In this study, the overarching goal is therefore to contribute toward a model that can link the *what* in citances with the *how*.

Methods

For the investigations reported in this paper, we have used the Semantic Scholar Open Research Corpus (Lo et al., 2020) as the source data for the analyses. For the analysis methods described below, we have analyzed the citances of a sample of 5,000 scientific articles uniformly distributed over the subject areas business, engineering, physics, medicine, and sociology. In the methodological description that follows, we have confined the investigation of citances to only include the immediately preceding sentence of a citation.

Citation roles

Verbs describe a form of practice, and from a practice-theoretical perspective loosely derived from Schatzki (1996), one could distinguish between dispersed and integrative practices. To identify the role of citances, we have extracted bigrams in the citances consisting of the word class pattern *verb + preposition* and ranked them according to their relative frequencies for analysis. For the upcoming investigations, we intend to more precisely determine which verb phrases that are indicative of citation roles and therefore can be expected to appear frequently in citation contexts, but infrequently elsewhere.

We have chosen an unsupervised approach to identify clusters of citation roles by focusing on the *verbs* contained in the extracted bigrams. To this end, we have applied the word2vec word embedding algorithm (see Mikolov et al., 2013) to assign semantic word vectors to the verbs contained in the bigrams. The verbs were visualized and clustered using the modularity optimization algorithm implemented in the Gephi visualization platform (see Blondel et al., 2008; Bastian et al., 2009).

Subject description

In order to identify the citance words that can be expected to be associated with the subject description of the associated references, we have extracted the *nouns* of the citances. The references in the research corpus were subsequently assigned representation vectors by weighting the nouns according to the normalized pointwise mutual information (NPMI), defined as follows. Let

$$NPMI(r, n) = \frac{\log_2(p(r, n)/(p(r)p(n)))}{I(r, n)}$$

where $p(r)$ denotes the probability of observing reference r in a citance, $p(n)$ denotes the probability of observing noun n in a citance, and $p(r, n)$ denotes the probability that reference r and noun n co-occur in the same citance. Moreover, $I(r, n)$ denotes the joint self-information of r and n , defined as

$$I(r, n) = -\log_2(p(r, n))$$

The NPMI scores have finally been scaled into the interval [0, 1], yielding the term weighting scheme

$$w_v(r, n) = (NPMI(r, n) + 1) / 2$$

We have also explored the potential of using an external vocabulary to enrich the subject descriptions of references by adding term weights for words that are closely semantically related to the observed nouns. To this end, we have employed word vectors generated by means of the GloVe word embedding algorithm (see Pennington et al., 2014). For the results reported in this paper we used a dataset consisting of 400,000 word vectors pretrained on the Wikipedia 2014 and Gigaword 5 corpora and published at <https://nlp.stanford.edu/projects/glove/>.

To each noun n extracted from the citances in the experiment corpus, we have identified a set W of the $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, 10\}$ words embedded in the word embedding space E having the highest cosine similarity with n . Each word in W has been weighted according to two different weighting schemes, which have been compared with respect to the resulting clustering effectiveness:

1. No separate weighting. The terms in W obtain the same weight as the associated noun.
2. Cosine similarity weighting. Let V be a vocabulary and $\eta: V \rightarrow E$ a function that associates words with their embedding vectors in E . Then we define

$$sim(t_i, t_j) = (\cos(\eta(t_i), \eta(t_j)) + 1) / 2$$

as a word similarity function normalized to the range $[0, 1]$. The terms $t_i \in T$ are weighted according to

$$w_\tau(r, t_i) = w_v(r, n) \times sim(n, t_i)$$

From the presented definitions, it immediately follows that the resulting weighting function w_τ yields a score in the range $[0, 1]$, which can be interpreted as the probability that a specific term in the vocabulary is associated with the subject of a specific reference.

Evaluation

In order to evaluate the quality of the generated subject descriptions for references, we have studied the clustering effectiveness of the resulting reference representation vectors. The methods employed to this end are the commonly used k -means clustering algorithm and the Rand index evaluation score (see e.g., Hubert & Arabie, 1985), the latter being defined as the ratio of pairs of items that have been correctly clustered according to a reference classification or clustering. The rationale behind using this evaluation approach is that we want to investigate the descriptive and discriminative capacity of the obtained subject descriptions without involving information inserted by the training of a classification model.

Preliminary results and discussion

In this section we present the preliminary results of the experiments conducted with regard to citation roles and subject descriptions in citances.

Citation roles

For this study, a sample of 5,000 of articles was used, uniformly distributed over five different fields of study: business, engineering, medicine, physics, and sociology. In figure 1, the graph

‘noted’, as well as the somewhat distinct group of terms at the bottom revolving around linguistic variants of verbs like ‘show*’, ‘indicate’, and ‘suggest’.

Figure 2. Nodes displayed in blue cluster of the diagram.

Lastly, in the orange cluster (see figure 3), verbs like ‘focused’, ‘drawing’, ‘depend’ are found, which seem to relate more heavily towards the active researcher’s activities.

Figure 3. Nodes displayed in the orange cluster of the diagram.

These traits become even more distinct when different disciplines, here identified by the *field of study*, are considered (see table 1).

Some activities are generally dispersed over all fields, such as *based [on]*, while phenomena are *found [in]* the physics and engineering fields and assumingly other researchers *found [that]* in the business and sociology fields. In the medical fields *found [in/that]* seem to be dispersed evenly in our data set.

Showed [that] and *showed [in]* are found in the more science-related fields, but references are not used to indicate that a phenomenon is *associated [with]* something else in the physics field. In the engineering, as well as the business fields, researchers relate to phenomena as *defined*.

It is within the sociology and business fields that researchers find the authors of cited references *argue [that]*, and it is also here, together with the medical field, to a lesser degree, that the references *suggest [that]*. It is also within these “softer” social sciences fields that researchers *focus [on] things*.

Table 1. The relative frequency of prepositional phrases in citances

PHYSICS		ENGINEERING		MEDICINE		BUSINESS		SOCIOLOGY	
based on	3,89%	based on	6,30%	associated with	4,95%	based on	4,56%	based on	2,25%
used in	2,00%	used in	1,74%	based on	2,62%	found that	1,32%	associated with	1,36%
given by	1,93%	used for	1,31%	shown that	1,77%	associated with	1,29%	is that	1,04%
found in	1,56%	associated with	1,13%	reported in	1,44%	is that	1,03%	found that	0,96%
discussed in	1,20%	reported in	1,12%	observed in	1,42%	suggests that	0,89%	focused on	0,87%
described in	1,14%	found in	1,09%	used in	1,32%	used in	0,84%	argued that	0,85%
obtained by	1,13%	described in	1,06%	showed that	1,26%	defined as	0,84%	suggest that	0,76%
presented in	1,05%	shown in	1,05%	compared with	1,16%	shown that	0,82%	seen as	0,76%
described by	1,01%	is that	1,03%	involved in	1,15%	focused on	0,66%	suggests that	0,55%
shown that	0,97%	proposed by	0,98%	found that	1,05%	used by	0,61%	focus on	0,52%
used for	0,82%	shown that	0,78%	found in	1,00%	is in	0,58%	engage in	0,52%
shown in	0,78%	developed by	0,68%	reported that	0,95%	argued that	0,57%	involved in	0,44%
observed in	0,78%	presented in	0,66%	suggested that	0,93%	suggest that	0,55%	developed by	0,44%
given in	0,78%	proposed in	0,64%	described in	0,86%	developed by	0,54%	suggested that	0,43%
proposed by	0,74%	defined as	0,61%	demonstrated that	0,86%	found in	0,52%	found in	0,42%
is in	0,74%	depending on	0,61%	suggest that	0,84%	are in	0,52%	argue that	0,42%
studied in	0,71%	compared with	0,59%	caused by	0,72%	engage in	0,51%	used in	0,42%
note that	0,65%	given by	0,57%	resulting in	0,64%	used as	0,50%	account for	0,41%
obtained in	0,59%	discussed in	0,55%	treated with	0,60%	seen as	0,50%	influenced by	0,39%
obtained from	0,57%	showed that	0,52%	is in	0,59%	shows that	0,47%	focusing on	0,39%
known as	0,57%	found that	0,52%	suggests that	0,55%	proposed by	0,45%	see for	0,38%
found that	0,55%	caused by	0,52%	characterized by	0,55%	show that	0,44%	defined as	0,38%
see for	0,53%	used as	0,51%	result in	0,51%	focus on	0,43%	is in	0,36%
is that	0,51%	given in	0,51%	reported by	0,51%	supported by	0,41%	used as	0,35%
known that	0,51%	consists of	0,51%	indicate that	0,50%	focusing on	0,41%	argues that	0,35%

Subject descriptions

For the evaluation of the clustering effectiveness of subject descriptions accumulated from associated citances, we used a collection of 2,518 references. The references have been preassigned to 20 field of study categories in the Semantic Scholar corpus, the frequency distribution of which is reported in table 2.

Table 2. Frequency distribution of the field of study for 2,518 references

Field of study	Frequency
Art	14
Biology	62
Business	332
Chemistry	25
Computer Science	201
Economics	469
Engineering	85
Environmental Science	8
Geography	17
Geology	9
History	23
Materials Science	15
Mathematics	76
Medicine	234
Philosophy	17
Physics	215
Political Science	96
Psychology	225
Sociology	353
[Uncategorized]	42
Total	2518

The accumulated subject descriptions have been evaluating by studying to what extent they contribute to a correct clustering of the references, as compared to the underlying field of study categorization of the references. The preliminary results are presented in table 3 and figure 4 below.

Table 3. Rand index for the clustering effectiveness of the extracted nouns and 0, 1, 2, ..., 10 semantically related terms, unweighted and cosine weighted respectively.

# of related terms	Rand index (unweighted terms)	Rand index (weighted terms)
0	0.3734	0.3734
1	0.4736	0.4966
2	0.4969	0.5976
3	0.5989	0.6186
4	0.467	0.5853
5	0.598	0.598
6	0.5478	0.6288
7	0.6137	0.6642
8	0.5524	0.6147
9	0.5005	0.6318
10	0.6317	0.6599

Figure 4. Rand index for the clustering effectiveness of the extracted nouns and 0, 1, 2, ..., 10 semantically related terms, unweighted and cosine weighted respectively.

What can be readily observed in the results is that the enrichment of the subject description vectors by means of semantically related words from an external vocabulary significantly increases the clustering effectiveness. Another observation that can be made is that the use of cosine weighting for the related words yields a generally higher Rand index score, as compared to using no weighting. A visualization of the references clustered by the modularization optimization algorithm of Gephi, with the underlying field of study categories displayed with colors, is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Visualization of the 2,518 analyzed references represented by nouns extracted from citances together with 7 semantically related words for each noun. Underlying field of study categories displayed as colors.

Conclusions

In this study, we have started to investigate how distinguishing the role of the cited reference from the subject of the cited reference can facilitate a more nuanced way to evaluate the citation context in the referring paper. Using natural language processing methods, we have developed methods to both enrich and distinguish specific traits in the aggregated citances. In future work we intend to extend the present analysis to a larger set of publications from the corpus and to cover more disciplines to be able to evaluate the results more precisely.

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